

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: COST EFFICIENCY WITH IOT, AI, AND BLOCKCHAIN

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Abstract: This paper explores the integration of digital technologies such as IoT, AI, and Blockchain in optimizing supply chain management (SCM). A mathematical model quantifies cost savings across inventory, lead times, and logistics. Findings reveal substantial cost reductions, enhancing business efficiency and competitiveness. Future research directions are discussed.

Key words: Digital technologies, supply chain management, Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), blockchain, cost efficiency, smart logistics, data analytics.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada IoT, sun'iy intellekt (SI) va blokcheyn kabi raqamli texnologiyalarning ta'minot zanjirini boshqarishni (SCM) optimallashtirishda qo'llanilishi o'rganiladi. Matematik model yordamida zaxiralar, yetkazib berish vaqti hamda logistika bo'yicha xarajatlarni tejash miqdori hisoblab chiqiladi. Natijalar xarajatlarning sezilarli darajada kamayganini, bu esa biznes samaradorligi va raqobatbardoshligini oshirganini ko'rsatadi. Kelgusidagi tadqiqot yo'nalishlari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli texnologiyalar, taqdimot zanjiri boshqaruvi, buyumlar interneti (IoT), sun'iy intellekt (AI), blokcheyn, nafillik, aqlli logistika, ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish.

Аннотация: В данной работе рассматривается интеграция цифровых технологий, таких как IoT, искусственный интеллект (ИИ) и Блокчейн, для оптимизации управления цепочками поставок (SCM). Математическая модель количественно оценивает экономию затрат на уровне запасов, времени выполнения заказов и логистики. Результаты показывают значительное снижение затрат, что повышает эффективность и конкурентоспособность бизнеса. Обсуждаются направления будущих исследований.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, управление цепями поставок, интернет вещей (IoT), искусственный интеллект (AI), блокчейн, экономическая эффективность, умная логистика, анализ данных.

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly interconnected and competitive global market, reducing product costs while maintaining quality poses a significant challenge for businesses. Supply chain management (SCM) plays a pivotal role in determining overall product costs and organizational efficiency. Traditional supply chains often encounter challenges such as poor visibility, high inventory costs, and extended lead times, which inflate overall expenses. However, the advent of digital technologies has introduced innovative methods to address these inefficiencies and optimize supply chain processes.

Technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Blockchain, and Big Data Analytics are transforming supply chain operations. IoT enables real-time tracking and monitoring of goods, AI facilitates predictive analytics and decision-making, Blockchain ensures transparency and security, and Big Data Analytics uncovers patterns for better forecasting. Collectively, these technologies empower organizations to establish responsive, efficient, and cost-effective supply chains.

This paper investigates the application of digital technologies in SCM to achieve cost reductions. By proposing a mathematical model, the study quantifies the impact of digital tools on supply chain costs and provides a practical framework for organizations aiming to optimize their operations.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The integration of digital technologies into supply chain management (SCM) has been widely studied, with scholars emphasizing their potential to enhance efficiency and reduce costs. Christopher highlights the importance of supply chain agility and the role of digital tools in enabling faster responses to market fluctuations [1]. Ivanov et al. discuss the transformative impact of artificial intelligence (AI) in predictive analytics, particularly in demand forecasting, which addresses overstocking and understocking challenges [2].

Blockchain technology, according to Saberi et al., enhances trust and transparency in supply chains by providing secure and immutable transaction records [3]. Similarly, Wang et al. investigate the role of Big Data Analytics in identifying inefficiencies and optimizing logistics operations [4]. Collectively, these studies underscore the potential of digital technologies to streamline supply chain processes and reduce associated costs.

Uzbek scholars have also contributed to this discourse. For instance, Rakhmonov explores the application of IoT in Uzbekistan's logistics sector, emphasizing its impact on real-time tracking and inventory management [5].

Despite extensive research, there remains a need for comprehensive mathematical models that quantify the cost reductions achieved through these technologies. This study addresses this gap by proposing a quantitative framework and analyzing its practical implications through a case study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a mixed-methods approach to evaluate the cost reduction benefits of digital technologies in supply chain management (SCM). A mathematical model is developed to quantify cost savings, integrating key variables such as inventory levels, lead times, transportation costs, and operational efficiencies. The model utilizes real-world data obtained from a mid-sized manufacturing company that recently digitized its supply chain using IoT, AI, and Blockchain technologies. The methodology comprises three phases:

Data Collection: Operational data, including inventory turnover rates, lead time fluctuations, and logistics costs, were collected over a 12-month period before and after the digital transformation. Secondary data was also gathered from industry reports and academic literature to validate the assumptions.

Model Development: A cost-saving formula was derived to evaluate the contributions of IoT, AI, and Blockchain in optimizing SCM. The model integrates technology-driven parameters with key cost drivers, enabling a robust quantification of savings.

Case Study Analysis: The model was applied to the collected data, and a comparative analysis was conducted to assess pre- and post-implementation efficiencies. Sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate the model's reliability across different scenarios.

This integrated methodology ensures a rigorous and actionable evaluation of the impact of digital technologies on supply chain costs.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The cost-saving model is represented as:

$$C_s = (C_b - C_d) + (E_i + E_l + E_t)$$

Where:

C_s : Total cost savings.

C_b : Baseline supply chain costs (pre-digital transformation).

C_d : Digital supply chain costs (post-digital transformation).

E_i : Efficiency gains in inventory management.

E_l : Efficiency gains in lead time reduction.

E_t : Efficiency gains in transportation and logistics.

Each efficiency gain component is calculated using the following sub-equations:

Inventory Efficiency (E_i):

$$E_i = H \cdot (I_b - I_d)$$

Where H is the holding cost per unit, I_b is the baseline inventory level, and I_d is the post-digital inventory level.

Lead Time Efficiency (E_l):

$$E_l = L \cdot (T_b - T_d)$$

Where L is the average order cost, T_b is the baseline lead time, and T_d is the post-digital lead time.

Transportation Efficiency (E_t):

$$E_t = F_b - F_d$$

Where F_b and F_d are baseline and digital transportation costs, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1. Cost efficiency gains in supply chain management.

Category	Baseline (Pre-Digital)	Post-Digital	Efficiency Gain	Cost Savings (\$)
Inventory Management	\$500,000	\$350,000	30%	\$150,000
Lead Time Reduction	\$200,000	\$160,000	20%	\$40,000
Transportation Efficiency	\$300,000	\$250,000	17%	\$50,000
Aggregate Costs	\$1,000,000	\$760,000	24%	\$480,000 (Total Savings)

Post-implementation, the IoT-enabled real-time tracking system reduced average inventory levels by 30%. Holding costs decreased from \$500,000 annually to \$350,000, resulting in an inventory efficiency gain (E_i) of \$150,000.

Predictive analytics powered by AI shortened average lead times by 20%, decreasing order costs from \$200,000 to \$160,000 annually. This led to a lead time efficiency (E_l) gain of \$40,000.

Blockchain's transparency minimized logistical errors, reducing annual transportation costs from \$300,000 to \$250,000. This contributed to a transportation efficiency (E_t) gain of \$50,000.

Applying the mathematical model:

$$C_s = (C_b - C_d) + (E_i + E_l + E_t)$$

$$C_s = (\$1,000,000 - \$760,000) + (\$150,000 + \$40,000 + \$50,000) = \$480,000$$

The total cost savings amounted to \$480,000 annually, representing a 24% reduction in overall supply chain costs (Table 2).

Table 2. Sensitivity analysis of cost savings.

Scenario	Holding Cost Fluctuation	Lead Time Variation	Estimated Savings (\$)
Base Scenario	±0%	±0%	\$480,000
Optimistic Scenario	-10%	-10%	\$500,000
Pessimistic Scenario	+10%	+10%	\$450,000

The model was tested under various scenarios to ensure robustness. For instance, with a 10% fluctuation in holding costs or lead time variations, the total savings ranged between \$450,000 and \$500,000, indicating the model's resilience.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The findings from this study underscore the transformative potential of digital technologies in optimizing supply chain management (SCM). By integrating IoT, AI, and Blockchain, organizations can achieve significant cost savings while enhancing operational efficiency. Specifically, IoT-enabled real-time tracking reduced inventory levels, thereby minimizing holding costs. AI-driven predictive analytics optimized lead times, facilitating faster and more cost-effective decision-making. Blockchain's transparency further enhanced logistical operations, reducing errors and fostering trust among supply chain partners.

The cost reduction of 24% observed in the case study highlights the substantial financial benefits of digitizing supply chains. Additionally, the sensitivity analysis demonstrated the robustness of the proposed mathematical model, with estimated savings remaining significant even under varying conditions. This resilience is critical for businesses operating in dynamic environments where cost parameters frequently fluctuate.

Despite the evident advantages, implementing digital technologies requires substantial initial investments, robust infrastructure, and skilled personnel. These challenges may deter smaller enterprises from adopting such solutions. Consequently, future research should explore scalable and cost-effective strategies for implementing these technologies in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

Furthermore, extending the model to include additional factors, such as energy consumption, environmental impacts, and customer satisfaction metrics, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the holistic benefits of digital transformation in SCM.

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